

CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE - EFFECT ON THE CLINICAL COURSE OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

¹**Izzatullayev Javohirbek**

2 st year student of Tashkent Medical Academy, Faculty of Medicine No. 2

²**Makhsudboyev Eldorbek**

1 st year student of Tashkent Medical Academy, Faculty of Medicine No. 2

³**Shaymatov Sherzod**

2 st year student of Tashkent Medical Academy, Faculty of Medicine No. 2

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Abstract. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is an independent nosological form, which is characterized by limitation of the air flow rate associated with the pathological inflammatory process in the lungs. This disease is one of the most common diseases in the world, its prevalence in different countries is from 6% to 26%. causes complications. Currently, special attention is paid to the study of OSOK risk factors, including urban air pollution, an increase in the amount of industrial dust, age, smoking, infectious diseases of the respiratory tract, their frequent exacerbations, obstructive lung. the condition of the disease is getting worse. In clinical practice, there are no standards for identifying comorbidities, treating physicians are not always focused on the search for concomitant pathology, which leads to late detection of cardiovascular pathology, as a result of which complications and mortality increase.

Key words: COPD, ischemic heart disease, arrhythmia, metabolic syndrome, arterial hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

OSOK takes the 4th place among the causes of death. According to WHO, by 2030, OSOK will be the third leading cause of death in the world. It is known that 50% of the total number of deaths in patients with COPD is caused by the presence of cardiovascular diseases, and the risk of death is 2-3 times higher, which is confirmed by a number of large population studies [5, 6]. According to various authors, the incidence of ischemic heart disease in patients with OSOK is 28-42% and increases significantly to 50.0-56.5% in older patients. Thus, one of the first studies published in Britain shows age-related patterns in the incidence of coronary heart disease and CAD based on an analysis of 5 million case histories. It was found that the risk of myocardial infarction increases 12 times in young patients with COPD; at the age of 35-45, the development of cardiovascular pathology in the presence of COPD is 7.6 times higher; Overall, patients with ACS are diagnosed with heart disease 5 times more often [7], and more than 50% of patients admitted to the hospital to reduce exacerbations of ACS have cardiovascular disease [8]. Arterial hypertension (AG) was detected in 62.2% of cases, and coronary artery disease (CVD) in 27% of patients with COPD. Purpose - to review the modern literature to determine the prevalence and early diagnosis of cardiovascular pathology in patients with OSOK, to determine the conditions and factors of the negative development of cardiovascular diseases based on the mechanisms of joint disease formation.

METHODS AND LITERATURE ANALYSIS

To prepare this article, PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus and other scientific databases were searched for keywords such as "Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease", "Combination of

Hypertension and COPD", "Ischemic Heart Disease and COPD". articles in English, Russian and Uzbek languages published from 2000 to 2023 were analyzed. In addition, diagnosis, treatment and prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease published in 2018 We studied the materials of the Global Strategy. The book "Early Diagnosis of Complications of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease" (methodical recommendation) of the Samarkand State Medical Institute of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan was used to summarize the information. Selected articles on etiology, pathogenesis, clinical symptoms, diagnostic methods, principles of treatment and prevention of complications were analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An international study that analyzed about 6,000 patients with OSOK showed that within 5 years, the cardiovascular system of this group of patients

vascular system diseases make up 25% of the total mortality. GROWING

Among the reasons for the first hospitalization of a patient with

42% are heart diseases. In OSOK, the main complications arising from the cardiovascular system are arterial hypertension, cardiac arrhythmia, ischemic heart disease, painless myocardial ischemia, and chronic cor pulmonale formation. When two pathological conditions exist, they aggravate each other. Now we will consider conditions such as Hypertension and OSAK, Ischemic heart disease and OSAK, Heart rhythm disorders and OSAK.

The combination of hypertension and COPD is one of the most common diseases, ranging from 6.8 to 76.3% in COPD patients, with an average of 34.3%, the prevalence of this pathology is increasing in normal patients. OSOK was found in every fourth patient with hypertension from 25 to 64 years old. Many studies proved the role of endothelial dysfunction in the mechanism of development of hypertension against the background of OSOK. At the same time, a direct relationship between the degree of blood pressure increase, the deterioration of bronchial obstruction and the severity of systemic inflammation and endothelial dysfunction was confirmed. The relationship between hypertension and OSOK is currently explained by two mechanisms of hypertension development. The first mechanism is the emergence of hypertension against the background of OSOK, which is present after 4-11 years (it is called "pulmogenic hypertension" - this term was proposed by NM Mukhorlyamov in 1966). The main characteristics of this type of hypertension are exacerbation of OSOK during treatment, an increase in blood pressure (A/B) occurs, and with the disappearance of broncho-obstructive syndrome, a decrease or normalization of blood pressure is observed. The second option for the development of hypertension explains the presence of hypertension as an independent disease in patients. According to many researchers, the main mechanism of systemic and pulmonary hypertension in OSOK is chronic arterial hypoxemia, which leads to activation of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone and sympathoadrenal systems.

Hypoxia is one of the causes of the activation of free radical and peroxidation processes with the formation of oxidative stress, which has a systemic nature and leads to the damage of the vessel wall and the formation of endothelial dysfunction, the development of rheological and aggregation disorders. Many studies have proved the role of endothelial dysfunction in the mechanism of development of hypertension against the background of COPD. At the same time, a direct relationship between the degree of blood pressure increase, the worsening of bronchial obstruction and the severity of systemic inflammation and endothelial dysfunction was confirmed [16]. in patients with hypertension, along with hypertension, there is a

violation of the elastic properties of arteries and an increase in the stiffness of the arterial wall. In patients with OSOK and hypertension, with normal and increased arterial stiffness, parameters of 24-hour blood pressure monitoring (circadian rhythms, average blood pressure values, load indicators) have a tendency to increase [14, 17]. According to a number of authors, clinical and functional characteristics of hypertension have been determined in patients with COPD. First of all, it is a violation of the daily profile of blood pressure lib, they are associated with the predominance of non-dipper and nocturnal picker types and, accordingly, insufficient reduction of nighttime blood pressure. Also, such patients show significant variability of systolic and diastolic blood pressure during the day, and a significant decrease in mean diastolic blood pressure showed that it increases [14, 16]. Ischemic heart disease and COPD. The prevalence of ischemic heart disease (IHD) in patients with COPD, according to different authors, is from 12% to 60%. Such differences are due to the use of different methods of diagnosing ischemic heart disease in studies and differences in the age of patients. depends. The detection rate of UIC increases significantly with age and depends on the severity of COPD, reaching 60% in its severe course. The pathogenesis of the development of coronary artery disease in patients with COPD is simultaneously It is associated with the involvement of several mechanisms - chronic systemic inflammation, hypoxia and oxidative stress, which contribute to the development of atherosclerosis. Thus, an increase in blood markers of systemic inflammation (interleukins 6,8, tumor necrosis factor- α , C-reactive protein) is associated with the development of ischemic heart disease. Anti-inflammatory cytokines are associated with the formation of atherosclerotic plaques. causes inflammation, development of inflammation, destabilization, increased platelet aggregation, thrombus formation and, as a result, against the background of reactions that increase the development of acute coronary syndrome [4, 18]. In addition, a number of authors in their research Endothelial-dependent and non-endothelial vasodilation in patients with COPD has been shown to be impaired compared to healthy subjects, which is associated with increased stiffness of the arterial wall. This factor plays an important role. plays a role, especially during exacerbation of COPD, promotes the development of atherosclerotic plaque rupture and myocardial infarction. At the same time, the ECLIPSE study and the BODE index indicated that the presence of ischemic heart disease in patients with COPD is associated with an increase in patient mortality [19]. an increase in concentration is observed. This fact predicts death within 30 days after exacerbation of OSOK [20]. In this regard, a large experience of patients has been conducted for a long time. Framingham and Gothenburg studies should be noted [20]. according to the results, it was determined that a 10% decrease in forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1) increases the risk of death from cardiovascular diseases by 28% and coronary events leading to death by 20%. According to research, O The most common clinical variant of YUIK in patients with COPD is the painless form (47-58%). This leads to the wrong diagnosis of YUIK, the development of acute myocardial infarction, and the manifestation of YUIK. Often, the appearance of cardialgia cannot always be considered by doctors as a manifestation of myocardial ischemia, especially when there are symptoms of cor pulmonale. Diagnosis of ischemic heart disease in patients with COPD is obscured by clinical signs, often is complicated by the inability to perform stress tests due to the presence of pain-free disease and severe dyspnea[18, 21]. As the severity of COPD increases, the frequency of episodes of silent myocardial ischemia increases [21]. Patients with frequent exacerbations of

COPD have been reported to have severe coronary artery damage (higher frequency and degree of stenoses). According to studies, acute coronary syndrome in patients with COPD has a number of features: a high frequency of atypical forms (mainly due to the asthmatic variant), an increase in the relative risk of paroxysmal atrial fibrillation [4, 22]. Also, myocardial infarction Early post-infarction angina is 2 times more common in patients with CKD, and recurrence of myocardial infarction is 4 times more likely. Studies have shown that patients with acute myocardial infarction due to OSOK have a higher in-hospital mortality rate. Thus, OSOK should be considered as an indicator of death from myocardial infarction, which is the most likely period for the development of fatal cardiovascular events during the exacerbation of SurGU. Therefore, during this period, patients in this group should be carefully monitored. Improving the diagnosis of ischemic heart disease in order to carry out early preventive and therapeutic measures in patients with CKD will help reduce the risk of fatal cases.

Heart rhythm disorder and GROWTH. OSOK. According to a number of epidemiological studies, arrhythmias are common in patients with OSOK. It is noted that the occurrence of arrhythmias is directly related to the severity of ventilation disorders depends on the size. The development of rhythm disturbances is caused by a number of pathogenetic factors: ischemic heart disease, hypertension, increased catecholamines, diselectrolyte disorders, respiratory alkalosis, and cardiac conduction system dysfunction [18]. It is caused by some drugs used to treat COPD. Thus, short-acting β_2 -adrenergic agonists have a proarrhythmogenic effect by prolonging the conduction time of impulses through the atrioventricular node, prolonging the QT interval, and can also cause hypokalemia and a decrease in chlorine concentration in the blood. Another side effect of taking drugs is the development of sinus tachycardia, which leads to the development of heart failure [18, 24]. The use of methylxanthines also contributes to the development of rhythm disturbances, even if these drugs are present in the blood in therapeutic concentrations. The proarrhythmogenic effect of methylxanthines It can be strengthened by taking macrolides and antihistamines. It has been shown that the incidence of different forms of arrhythmia varies significantly and depends on the severity of COPD, the presence of signs of cor pulmonale, and concomitant ischemic heart disease. Thus, supraventricular rhythm disorders such as sinus tachycardia, trial extrasystole, and paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia are more often observed in patients with mild forms of COPD. The frequency of supraventricular arrhythmias in patients with severe COPD It is about 70%. Arterial fibrillation in COPD patients is related to lung ventilation dysfunction and occurs more often than in the general population. It was also found that atrial fibrillation occurs 2 times more often with FEV1 <60% in patients with COPD [18]. With the development of chronic pulmonary heart disease, ventricular arrhythmias dominate the composition of rhythm disorders. 68-83 In % of cases, this is a high-grade ventricular arrhythmia, which can cause sudden death in patients with COPD [2, 3, 18]. is accompanied by an increase to % [18]. Sudden death in patients with COPD is relatively frequent during the exacerbation of the disease and is 14%. Logistic regression analysis shows that patients with COPD identified 4 independent risk factors for sudden death in patients with COPD: age, alveolar-arterial gradient above 41 mmHg, arterial ventricular tachycardia, atrial fibrillation. It is indicated during exacerbation in the presence of symptoms of cardiovascular pathologies and chronic pulmonary heart disease. Timely detection of life-threatening arrhythmias reduces the risk of sudden death in these patients.

CONCLUSION

And clinical features of cardiovascular pathology in patients with COPD have been sufficiently studied, and the side effects of cardiovascular diseases have been sufficiently studied. The pathogenesis of the phenomena has been determined. However, in real clinical practice, there are no standards for diagnosing joint diseases. Treating physicians are not always focused on the search for concomitant pathology, which leads to late detection of cardiovascular pathology, resulting in increased complications and mortality. Prognostic factors for the development of unconscious events are the presence of severe obstructive disorders of the respiratory system, frequent exacerbation of OSOK, ventricular dysfunction. Diagnosis and treatment recommendations for patients with COPD should include cardiovascular diagnostic methods, especially in exacerbations and severe cases, such as echocardiography, Holter ECG monitoring, and 24-hour blood pressure monitoring, which allows timely detection of pathological conditions.

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